

The effect of a semi-industrial masterbatch process on the carbon nanotube agglomerates and its influence in the properties of thermoplastic carbon nanotube composites

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ABSTRACT

The present study details an industrial process to prepare polypropylene (PP) composites reinforced with different loadings (0.5-10wt.%) of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) from a direct dilution of a masterbatch produced by an optimised extrusion compounding process. The work demonstrates how the anisotropy in the distribution of CNTs can have a positive effect on the electrical conductivity and fracture toughness of the resulting composites. The composite with the highest loading of CNTs had an electrical conductivity of 10^{-2} S/m comparable to those reported in the available literature. The composites showed anisotropy in their properties that seems to be caused by the non-homogeneous distribution of the agglomerates produced by the orientation of the flow direction during the injection process. The composites produced in this work exhibited a fracture toughness up to 55% higher than neat PP and failed by polymer ductile tearing. It was found that the CNT agglomerates distributed throughout the matrix increased the toughness of PP by promoting plastic deformation of the matrix during the fracture process and by a slight load transfer between the polymer matrix and the CNTs of the agglomerates.

INTRODUCTION

It has been reported that addition of a small amount of nanofillers can lead to significant enhancement of properties in polymeric materials. Consequently, extensive research has been carried out in the field of nanocomposites that consist of a polymeric matrix and carbon-based nanofillers, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs)¹⁻³ and nanofibres^{4,5}, graphene^{3,6,7}, graphite nanoplates⁸⁻¹⁰, among others. To take advantage of these nanofillers, an homogeneous dispersion of the nanofiller in the matrix is necessary¹¹. For thermoplastic polymers, solution mixing¹² or in situ polymerization¹³ are probably the most effective techniques for nanosized filler dispersion. However, these

techniques require a lot of reagents (monomers, solvents, chemical products for functionalization), are very time consuming (solvent removal, polymerization reaction, functionalization or grafting reaction), and typically environmentally unfriendly.

From an industrial perspective, melt compounding is a highly desirable processing technique approach to produce thermoplastic nanocomposites because it is compatible with conventional processing techniques used in the thermoplastic industry, such as extrusion or injection moulding. Most of the studies reported used injection-moulding machines and a few grams of material, the processing characteristics of which do not correspond to industrial

equipment^{14–23}. The injection pressure, mould temperatures, and volume of sample are some of the parameters that will affect the characteristics of the material obtained. For CNTs thermoplastic composites, these process parameters affects the dispersion of the nanofiller on the polymer matrix: CNTs agglomerate disentanglement and orientation, break-up and orientation of dispersed individual CNTs^{24,25}, formation of new secondary agglomerates^{26,27}, etc. For example, injection-moulded samples use to have anisotropic properties dependant on the polymer chains and filler processing-induced orientation^{28–30}

However, the majority of these studies only analysed the electrical properties of thin films of CNTs composites but just a few of them also included mechanical -tensile and flexural- properties (strength, modulus and/or strain at break) and impact resistance properties^{31–34}. As it is well known, impact tests cannot evaluate how a material will resist crack initiation and growth when loaded at low speed, i.e. quasi-statically. Recently, we performed one of the few studies in fracture toughness with a PP matrix reinforced with graphite nanoplates (GNP)³⁵.

In this work, we have prepared and characterized PP/CNTs composites made by direct dilution of a highly loaded masterbatch. A highly concentrated mixture of polymer and nanofiller (masterbatch) is produced by extrusion compounding, followed by a direct dilution to achieve the desired concentration by injection moulding of the required amount of masterbatch pellets into the polymer matrix to achieve the nanocomposite with the desired nanofiller content. The use of masterbatches is highly desired by plastic converters as it avoids the direct handling of hazardous materials, this is more remarked when dealing with CNTs and other nanomaterials. The effect of the direct dilution on the injection machine will be evaluated in the present work to determine the limitations and drawbacks of the proposed solution. The aim of the present work is to

demonstrate the feasibility of using a direct dilution of a CNT masterbatch on an injection machine. In general in literature there are several examples that are focused on the determination on how the filler agglomerates undergo dispersion by rupture and erosion mechanisms, which usually occur simultaneously^{14,36,37}. These processes are based on the determination of the optimal conditions in the extruder, optimizing temperatures, profiles, etc^{38,39}. Although these studies have demonstrated that optimal conditions resulted in better performances, the effect of the extra steps required and the costs makes this process not always the most efficient. There are examples in literature that are focused on the determination of the use of the direct dilution of masterbatches in injection processes⁴⁰. From an industrial point of view the elimination of extra steps in the use of nanocomposites is envisaged for the industry as it reduces costs and negative impacts. The present works aims to determine the potential use of direct dilution of masterbatches as a cost effective process for nanocomposites adoption. In our study the results pointed out some benefits of the direct dilution as the electrical conductivity obtained are among the highest described in literature for PP nanocomposites.

The CNT dispersion was studied by scanning and transmission electron microscopy (SEM and TEM). The anisotropy of the injection-moulded specimens was analysed by measuring the electrical conductivity in three dimensions.

Analysis of the fracture behaviour of the PP/CNTs composites produced was also carried out by applying the same method as in our previous work, the S_{pb} parameter method³⁵. The fracture study included a digital image correlation (DIC) analysis of the deformation zone in front of the crack tip, during fracture tests, and a fracture surface analysis by SEM.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Commercially available PP impact copolymer (Hifax EP3080), acquired from Lyondell Basell, with a density of 900kg/m³ and a melt flow index (230°C/2.16kg) of 7.5g/10min (ISO 1133), was used for the production of the PP/CNTs nanocomposites. The commercially-acquired 90% purified multi-walled CNTs (NC7000), produced by catalytic chemical vapour deposition, were available commercially from Nanocyl S.A., and were used with no further treatment. The individual CNT had an average diameter of 9.5nm and an average length of 1.5µm.

Masterbatch production by extrusion-compounding

A polypropylene masterbatch with 10wt.% of CNTs was prepared by using an industrial extrusion-compounding machine (Coperion ZSK 26) equipped with a 26mm diameter co-rotating twin-screw and with two Brabender gravimetric feeders. The optimal conditions were selected using different screw configurations, processing conditions and evaluating their results on CNT dispersion. Temperature profile and high shear screw profile were used to ensure proper dispersion. The polymer pellets and the powdery CNTs were introduced by the main feeder and the side feeder, respectively. The molten polymer and nanofiller were mixed at a screw speed of 500rpm. The temperature of the resulting mixture was increased from 170°C in the feeding zone to 190°C at the nozzle. The compounding was extruded through a 2mm diameter die at a constant output rate of 5kg/h to give 10kg of masterbatch. The extrudate strand was quenched immediately in a water bath at room temperature, dried and cut into small pellets. For the pure PP samples, PP pellets were also extruded following the same process.

Sample preparation by injection-moulding

Dog-bone shaped specimens (type 1A) for tensile tests, under ISO 527^{41,42}, and specimens for flexural tests, under ISO 178⁴³, were injected into a specific mould made in tool steel 1.2790, at a temperature of 30°C. The masterbatch pellets

were dried at 80°C for 4 hours prior to processing. Composites were prepared by diluting the masterbatch with neat PP until the desired concentration (0.5, 1.0, 2.5 and 5.0wt.%) and the specimens produced by injection moulding through a JSW 85 EL II injection machine with a 35mm diameter reciprocating screw, at a screw speed of 131rpm. The temperature of the mixture was increased from 225°C at the barrel to 255°C at the nozzle. Pure PP samples were also prepared using the extruded PP to be used as reference.

Morphological analysis of the samples

The microstructural analysis of the as received flexural test specimens was performed by scanning electron microscopy (Helios NanoLab 600i). To analyze the agglomerates in the transverse direction the specimen, two notches were machined on both sides of specimen to create a flat crack surface. The specimen was cooled in liquid nitrogen and immediately broken transversally into two halves at high speed by impacting it with a hammer. A similar process have been followed to analyze the agglomerates in the longitudinal direction of the specimen. The surfaces of the broken specimens were analysed by SEM using both secondary and backscattered electron detectors (Figure 1). To study the CNTs agglomerates morphology, it has been measured from SEM micrographs the equivalent planar diameter $d = (4 \times \text{area} / \pi)^{1/2}$, and the shape factor defined as:

$$F = 4\pi \times \text{area} / (\text{perimeter})^2 \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Note that F ranges between 1 and 0. F=1 corresponds to a circle and it decreases as particles becomes elongated. Such measurements were performed parallel and perpendicular to the injection flow direction.

Thin samples (40nm thickness) were also prepared by ultra-microtomy under cryogenic conditions and observed by Transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL-2000 FXIIa).

Electrical conductivity characterization

The electrical conductivity of the injection-moulded nanocomposites was measured in the three dimensions of the sample. To perform these measurements, cubic samples with a side of 5 mm were cut from the prismatic bars injected for flexural tests. The faces perpendicular to the desired direction, in which the electrical conductivity was to be measured, were subjected to a polishing process to ensure a smooth surface. The samples were then cleaned in an ultrasound bath with ethanol to remove the abrasive particles left behind as a result of the polishing process. The polished surfaces were coated with silver paste to ensure good contact between the sample surface and the electrode. The sample was sandwiched between two copper electrodes connected to a digital multimeter (Agilent 34410A 6 1/2 Digit multimeter). At least three samples were measured per material. The electrical conductivity (σ) was calculated following Eq. 2:

$$\sigma=L/RA \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where L is the length of the specimen (distance between the surfaces coated with silver paste), R is the resistance measured by the multimeter and A is the area of the sample (area of the faces coated with silver paste).

Mechanical and thermal characterization

Analysis of tensile and flexural properties was conducted under ambient conditions with a Zwick Roell Z 10KN. At least 10 specimens were measured for each composite. Tensile tests were carried out in accordance with standard ISO 527 with an initial gauge length of 50mm and a crosshead speed of 1mm/min during linear tensile stretching, which was increased to 50mm/min until failure. Flexural tests were carried out in accordance with standard ISO 178 with a cross-head speed of 2mm/min. Specimens were tested in a three-point bending configuration with a distance of 57mm between supports.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed on samples cut

from the dog-bone specimens and measured on a DSC Q200 (TA Instruments). During analysis, samples were heated 20–220°C at a rate of 10°C/min, held at 220°C for 0.5min to eliminate any thermal history, and then cooled to 20°C at a rate of 10°C/min. Then, after being kept at 20°C for 0.5min, samples were heated to 220°C at a rate of 10 °C/min³⁵. The crystallinity of the nanocomposites has been determined by the integration of the melting region of the DSC curve on the second heating curve in order to suppress any thermal history.

Analysis of the quasi-static fracture behaviour of PP nanocomposites was carried out by following a three-point bending test, with a span to width ratio of 4, by using single edge-notch bending specimens with a length of 62.6mm, a width of 13mm, and a thickness of 5mm. To apply the S_{pb} parameter, blunt-notched and pre-cracked specimens have to be tested. A detailed explanation of the S_{pb} parameter method can be found elsewhere^{44–47}.

To analyse the PP/CNTs nanocomposites, one blunt-notched reference specimen and two pre-cracked specimens were tested for each concentration. The reference specimens had blunt notches 10.5±0.1mm in length, which were made with a disk-cutting machine. The pre-cracked specimens were prepared from an initial blunt notch, of 3.0±0.2mm by sharpening the notch by tapping with a razor blade to extend the crack length to 3.9±0.2mm. Fracture tests were performed by an universal electromechanical testing machine (Instron 3384) at room temperature and with a crosshead speed of 1mm/min^{35,44}.

Fractographic analysis and digital image correlation

After fracture tests, the specimens were cooled down in liquid nitrogen and immediately shattered to generate a brittle fracture surface to allow easy identification of the ductile fracture surface generated during the fracture

test. The surfaces of the broken specimens were sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold (~ 20 nm) and analysed by SEM (EVO MA15, Zeiss)³⁵.

To identify the plastic deformation zone that is generated in front of the crack tip during the fracture toughness test, one side of every specimen was painted white and a random black speckle pattern was painted for DIC analysis³⁵. Images were recorded every 3s during the test. The area of interest was located immediately in front of the root of the blunt notch ($13 \times 6.5 \text{ mm}^2$). Evaluation of the acquired images was carried out using the Vic-2D 2009 software (VicSNAP, Correlated Solutions Inc.).

FIGURE 1 a) Scheme of the surfaces analyzed. b) and c) Backscattered electron SEM micrographs of the cryogenically fractured surfaces of a 5wt.% CNTs specimen observed along and perpendicular to the injection direction, respectively. The CNTs agglomerates are clearly aligned along the longitudinal direction (red surface, X-axis). Inset shows a high-magnification image of an agglomerate.

FIGURE 2 TEM micrograph of a thin film obtained by ultra-microtomy of nanocomposite with 10wt.% concentration. The micrograph shows the dispersion degree of the CNTs obtained in the masterbatch with individual tubes and small aggregates and the presence of larger aggregates

RESULTS

CNT dispersion and electrical conductivity

SEM of the cryogenically fractured surface of all the samples were analysed. The neat PP sample showed some micron-scaled platelets. These platelets were composed of silicon and oxygen among other elements, which have been added to enhance the processability or heat stability of the raw material.

For all the composite samples, CNT agglomerates were observed (Figure 1). The surface image of the 5wt.% CNT composite is shown in FIGURE 1b, in which large agglomerates wide were observed. These agglomerates may have been formed during the re-melting corresponding to the injection-moulding step, as the re-agglomeration process of CNTs can be thermally activated and accelerated by shear flow^{37,48}.

Interestingly, these agglomerates seem to have a preferred orientation as seen in FIGURE 1. It is well known that the injection process produces an anisotropy in the filler distribution, for CNTs^{28–30}, carbon nanofibres²¹, talc⁴⁹, and short carbon and glass fibre⁵⁰ polymer composites. Because of the high shear forces produced during injection and the high viscosity of the molten polymer, the agglomerates seems to be elongated following the polymer flow²⁴. The shape factor have been calculated for the 5 and 10wt.% CNT samples. For the other materials, it have not been possible to find enough agglomerates to have a statistic.

No significant changes have been found in the agglomerate size for both the 5 and 10wt.% CNT composites. As the 5wt.% CNT sample have been diluted with raw PP, it seems that during the dilution process there are not build-up or destruction²⁶ of agglomerates. On the other hand, the shape factor remained unaffected by the dilution process, with a value of 0.4 and 0.8 along the longitudinal and transverse direction respectively, for both 5 and 10wt.% composites (Table 1 and Figure 1a). This indicates a clear elongation of CNTs agglomerates along the injection flow direction ($F=0.4$) compared to the transverse direction ($F=0.8$), which is undoubtedly generated by the geometry of the injection process.

Table 1. Size and shape factor of the CNTs agglomerates presented in the longitudinal (longit.) and transverse direction (trans.)

Material	Direction	Agglomerate size (μm)	Shape factor
PP + 5 CNTs	Longit.	40.8 ± 13.7	0.42 ± 0.07
PP + 10 CNTs	Longit.	41.8 ± 15.5	0.44 ± 0.08
PP + 5 CNTs	Trans.	45.2 ± 20.8	0.81 ± 0.03
PP + 10 CNTs	Trans.	44.1 ± 17.4	0.80 ± 0.04

The TEM micrographs confirmed a good dispersion and homogeneous distribution of the

CNTs within the composite for all the samples (FIGURE 2). No significant changes have been found for the agglomerates presented in the undiluted and diluted samples indicating that the direct dilution of the masterbatch on the injection process results effective. Thus, we can conclude that the presented strategy can be directly implemented by the plastic sector as no specific dispersion approaches are required. The benefits of using masterbatches in direct dilution had been already highlighted in the introduction.

As expected, CNT orientation affects the properties of the sample. For electrical conductivity highly anisotropy behaviour has been measured. Depending on the direction of the sample (Figure 3), the amount of filler at which the material experiences a sharp increase in the electrical conductivity, known as the percolation threshold, is 2.5-5wt.% of CNTs for the X and Y direction and 5-10wt.% of CNTs for the Z direction. The electrical conductivity obtained for the 10wt.% sample is comparable to other CNTs composites^{2,20,23,29,34,51-54}. At the present work, the high conductivity obtained at industrial scale is relevant for industrial applications. This value may result from the large elongated agglomerates formed and the anisotropy effect, in which the conductivity in the X direction is 6×10^{-2} S/cm, but only 2×10^{-2} S/cm and 2×10^{-5} S/cm in the Y and Z directions, respectively.

FIGURE 3 Electrical conductivity measurements obtained in this work for the PP/CNTs composites, compared to some values reported

for PP composites made by melt mixing^{2,20,23,29,34,51-54}. A schematic representation of the injection moulded bars and the three directions for which electrical conductivity was measured are shown. The injection-moulding direction corresponds to the X axis, the width corresponds to the Y axis, and the thickness corresponds to the Z axis. The values of electrical conductivity obtained are comparable to those reported in works that have used treated CNTs³⁴, different injection moulding velocities²⁹, two-roll mill⁵³ or small-scale mixing machines^{20,23}.

Mechanical properties

The tensile modulus and tensile strength increase with CNT content (Figure 4a). The tensile strength improvements (10% for the composite with 10wt.% CNT) seem to indicate that the debonding of particles does not take place prior to the start of plastic deformation⁵⁵. Both the flexural modulus and flexural strength show similar trends with slight increases too with CNT weight fraction (Figure 4b).

This modest enhancement in mechanical properties, relative to some reported in the literature^{33,56}, can be attributed, among others, to the presence of agglomerates and the relatively weak effect of the CNTs on crystallization behaviour¹². The melting temperature (T_m) of neat PP is 164.1°C, whereas for the PP/CNTs composites it is 163.8 ± 0.1 °C. The crystallization temperature (T_c) of neat PP is 123.6°C, which is similar to the T_c of the composites 124.1 ± 0.3 °C. From calculations we find that the degree of crystallinity (X_c)³⁵ is almost the same for the PP and PP/CNTs samples (27.7 and 28.6 ± 2.1 %, respectively). There is no significant effect of the CNTs on the melting and crystallization of PP^{28,34,56}. Thus, based on the results obtained, there is no nucleating effect and change on the crystalline phase of the polymeric matrix.

In Figure 4c, the average value of the fracture toughness, J_{IC} , calculated from the two

specimens tested for each CNT content is presented. The best result, a fracture toughness a 55% higher than that of neat PP, with a loading of just 0.5wt.% CNTs, is larger than the highest improvement obtained for PP/GNPs composites³⁵. Ganß et al.²⁸ analysed the resistance to quasi-static crack growth initiation on PP/CNTs composites in which the CNTs have a higher dispersion degree than those in the present study. They found that resistance decreased with addition of up to 5wt.% CNTs, except for 1.5wt.% at which an increase of 25% was measured. This effect was attributed to hindrance of the ductile yield as a result of polymer wrapping and the immobilized polymer layer at the polymer-nanofiller interface. However, in the present study, the J_{IC} values obtained by application of the S_{pb} parameter method show that by increasing the amount of CNTs from 0.5 to 10wt.%, the improvements were not as good as those achieved for 0.5wt.% CNTs, even though the composites have a higher fracture toughness than the neat matrix.

FIGURE 4 a) Normalized tensile modulus and strength; b) normalized flexural modulus and strength as a function of nanofiller content for PP/CNTs nanocomposites; c) Crack growth initiation energy, J_{IC} , for PP/CNTs nanocomposites. The fracture toughness increases with the addition of CNTs. The maximum increase is achieved for a nanocomposite is 0.5wt.% CNTs, which has a value 55% higher than neat PP

Digital image correlation (DIC) and SEM analysis of fracture surfaces

Pictures taken during the fracture tests were processed by DIC to obtain the strain field in the principal direction, ε_1 . This is the direction in which the major principal stresses take place and, in the testing configuration of the fracture tests, this direction is approximately equal to the longitudinal direction of the single edge-notched bend specimen (FIGURE 5a). A comparison performed between the full-field total strain obtained for PP (FIGURE 5b) and the nanocomposites with 0.5 and 10wt.% of CNTs (FIGURE 5c and 5d, respectively) at the moment of the fracture initiation shows a change in size of the deformation zone in front of the crack tip. The strain provided has both an elastic and plastic component. However, to identify the crack growth initiation by the S_{pb} parameter method, it is necessary to fully reach the plastic zone^{45,46}. Because this requirement was met for all the materials analysed, the plastic component is assumed to be the predominant component of the deformation shown in FIGURE 5. It is well known that the shape of the plastic zone in front of the crack tip changes with the transition from plain stress conditions at the specimen surface, to plain strain conditions at the mid-thickness section⁵⁷. However, for this comparison it is assumed that the plastic deformation zone has a cylindrical shape along the thickness of the single edge-notched bend specimen.

FIGURE 5 Results obtained from DIC analysis. a) Area of interest analysed by DIC. The inset shows the root of the blunt notch and the sharp pre-crack (indicated by the dotted line). The principal direction is approximately equal to the longitudinal direction of the single edge-notched bend specimen; b) Strain field in the principal direction, ϵ_1 , obtained by DIC at the moment of fracture initiation during the fracture toughness tests for neat PP; c) Nanocomposite with 0.5wt.% of CNTs, which is the material with the highest fracture toughness; and d) 10wt.% CNT nanocomposite.

In the PP matrix, the region of the specimen with a deformation smaller or equal to 4.5% is 54mm³ (FIGURE 5b). The volume of this region increases by 145% to 132mm³ in the nanocomposite with 0.5wt.% of CNTs (FIGURE 5c). This increase in size may indicate that large plastic strain has taken place in the zone in front of the crack tip. In the case of the 10wt.% CNT nanocomposite (FIGURE 5d), the size of this region increases by 50% relative to neat PP, with a volume of approximately 80mm³. These results are in agreement with those obtained in our previous work for PP/graphite nanoplates composites³⁵ in which an increase in fracture toughness corresponds to an increase in size of the deformed region.

Once the fracture toughness tests were complete, the fracture surfaces of the specimens were analysed by SEM. By observation of the

fracture surface of PP (FIGURE 6a) the failure mechanism was seen to be polymer ductile tearing by void nucleation and growth. This mechanism was also observed in the fracture surfaces of nanocomposites (FIGURE 6b and 6c). The fracture mechanism of the nanocomposites is matrix ductile tearing, which has been reported for PP composites with graphite nanoplates³⁵, Al₂O₃ nanoparticles, SiO₂ nanoparticles, nanoclays, CaCO₃ microparticles⁵⁸, and PE composites with CaCO₃ microparticles⁵⁹. However, relative to our previous work on PP/graphite nanoplatelets composites, the CNT agglomerates were not completely debonded after the fracture test, as confirmed by SEM (FIGURE 7). It seems that stress concentrates around the CNT agglomerate during fracture tests, which acts as a soft particle during this process^{60,61}. Thus, the high stress state generated is released by

FIGURE 6 Ductile tearing region in the fracture surface of a) neat PP; b) 0.5wt.% CNT nanocomposite; and c) 10wt.% CNT nanocomposite in which large CNT agglomerates can be seen. The arrow indicates the crack growth direction.

Deformation of the polymer around the agglomerate. The polymer around the CNTs agglomerates can be deformed plastically into fibrils, however the CNTs of the surface of the agglomerate remained bonded to the polymer (FIGURE 7a). As the polymer around the agglomerate plastically deforms, there is somehow a slight load transmission from the matrix to the CNTs. The process allows dissipation of energy, which may explain the improvement of the fracture toughness of the PP/CNTs composites relative to neat PP. It is known that the number and size of nanofiller agglomerates increase with increased nanofiller loading^{28,56,62}. Thus, after the fracture toughness reaches its maximum at 0.5wt.% CNTs, the J_{IC} decreases because this value is the result of two important facts: the energy dissipated by deformation of the polymer around the agglomerates versus the effect of the larger agglomerates as sources of secondary cracks⁵⁹. For CNT weight fractions higher than 0.5%, the net balance between both effects seems to be positive because all the values for fracture toughness are higher than that of neat PP.

FIGURE 7 a) SEM image of a CNT agglomerate located within the deformation zone in front of the crack tip in a 0.5wt.% CNT composite; b) Inset from a) in which the external CNTs of the agglomerate are still bonded to the plastically deformed polymer around the agglomerate.

CONCLUSIONS

Commercial-grade CNTs were efficiently integrated into a PP matrix by following a solvent-free approach known as the masterbatch technique. The obtained materials show good and homogeneous distribution of the CNT, however it was not possible to completely break up and disperse these agglomerates in the matrix. Despite the presence of these agglomerates, the electrical conductivity obtained above the percolation threshold is among the highest conductivities reported in the literature^{2,20,23,29,34,51–54}. The electrical conductivity also shows that the processing method induced a certain anisotropy to the samples obtained, which is in agreement with the elongation of the agglomerates presented in matrix. Also the agglomerate size and orientation seem not to be affected by the dilution process.

Moderate improvements in tensile and flexural properties as CNT content increases indicates that the addition of CNTs does not significantly affect the PP matrix, because all the materials have almost the same glass transition, melting and crystallization temperatures as well as similar degrees of crystallinity.

Addition of CNTs improves the fracture toughness of PP, for all nanofiller loadings up to 55% higher for the 0.5wt.% PP/CNTs composite, which turned out to have the largest deformation zone. It was seen that CNT agglomerates promote plastic deformation of the matrix during the fracture process, similarly as the cavitation or debonding mechanism of microparticles dispersed in a thermoplastic polymer. This, along with the slight load transfer from the matrix to the CNTs, during deformation, explains the enhancement in fracture toughness.

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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TITLE

The effect of a semi-industrial masterbatch process on the carbon nanotube agglomerates and its influence in the properties of thermoplastic carbon nanotube composites

TEXT

To take advantage of the outstanding properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), much research effort has been invested to obtain a homogeneous dispersion of nanofiller in a thermoplastic matrix by using small-scale mixing. However, the addition of CNT agglomerates to polypropylene using an industrial approach, can have a positive effect on the matrix. Resulting in a toughened polymeric material with improved mechanical properties and high electrical conductivity.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT FIGURE

